

DESIGN OF A WIRELESS CAPACITIVE POWER TRANSFER SYSTEM

Xin Wang and Bowen Li

School of Equipment Engineering

Shenyang Ligong University,

Shenyang, China, 110168

Emails: ltqbw1991513@sina.com

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Abstract- This paper presents the design of a capacitive power transfer (CPT) system by using the Class-E amplifier approach. The Class-E amplifier approach is chosen to be adopted since it produces high efficiency as close as to 100%, theoretically. Based on the Class-E approach, a design of wireless power transfer system is used to transfer power to a LED lamp. The system has an output around 4.2 watts at a distance of 2 millimeters which transfer enough output power to light a LED lamp. Simulation and experimental results are carried out to verify the high efficiency of the Class-E amplifier. Finally, the design of practical wireless LED lamp is achieved.

Index terms: *Class-E amplifier; capacitive power transfer; ZVS condition; Additional capacitor; LED.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless power transfer system plays a significant role in the modern technology of power supply application. Wireless charging has been extensively utilized in portable devices such as smartphones, laptops and even some medical devices [1]. Besides, wireless power transfer can be used to replace mechanical connections while delivering power for industrial purposes [2]. Thus, a higher efficiency of the system can be achieved and the cost can be decreased at the same time. Besides making their way in delivering power to portable devices and industrial facilities, wireless power transfer systems play an emerging role in medical applications. Implantable medical devices nowadays receive international attentions and play a significant role in modern medicines. Wireless transfer of power to these devices, such as sensing, drug delivery and local stimulation, can reduce the risks of battery replacement while surgery is taking place [3]. It is possible to use wireless power transfer to supply power to implant devices. This is a much more convenient and safer method to replacing implanted batteries [4].

Figure 1. Basic schematic of Class-E amplifier

Figure 1 shows the basic schematic of the Class-E amplifier [5] [6]. The Class-E Amplifier is a switching power inverter/amplifier which can perform the Class-B or Class-C amplifiers [7] in regards to the level of efficiency. The shunt capacitor, C_p , as seen in Figure 1, is a key component of the Class-E amplifier to achieve a high working efficiency [8]. The waveform of the shunt capacitor is the main reason of high working efficiency [9-11]. MOSFET can be used as a switch for the Class-E amplifier. The switching losses can be reduced significantly, especially during

switching transitions, mainly because the switch-off voltage and switch-on current cannot be applied on the MOSFET simultaneously [12]. In order to reduce the power dissipation of the switch to a minimum, the circuit was designed to make the voltage across the shunt capacitor to be zero when the switch turns on. Thus, no power will be lost on the switch. To be specific, zero voltage switching and zero current switching conditions are the optimal operation for the Class-E amplifier. In this case, only zero voltage switching condition has to be satisfied under the sub-optimal operation.

In this paper, the operation of the zero voltage switching (ZVS) condition for Class-E amplifier will be analyzed and used in the design. The Class-E amplifier has a wider range of shunt capacitance, switching frequency and load resistance under the ZVS condition, which increases the tolerance of the capacitive power transfer system. Suetsugu and Kazimierczuk also propose that there is no difference between ZVS and ZCS condition if only switching loss is considered.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the Class-E amplifier under ZVS operating condition. A schematic of capacitive power transfer system will be presented in Section III. Section IV shows the simulation of the circuit in LTSPICE for the proposed capacitive power transfer system. Experimental results will then be discussed in Section V. Section VI shows the practical design of the CPT system for wireless power transfer to a LED lamp, and conclusions will then be drawn in Section VII.

II. CLASS-E AMPLIFIER

This paper analyses the circuit of the Class-E amplifier shown in Fig. 1. The following assumptions are carried out for the derivations of design equations [13].

- 1) The inductance of the choke coil L is large enough so that the current ripple can be neglected.
- 2) The DC voltage drop across the choke is zero because zero internal resistance is assumed.
- 3) The MOSFET on-resistance transistor is zero.
- 4) The MOSFET turns on and off instantly.

The derivations of design equation of Class-E amplifier have been described previously by Kimber [14].

The output power of the CPT system is described by

$$P_0 = \frac{8V_{cc}^2}{\pi^2 R} \cos^2 \phi \quad (1)$$

Where

V_{cc} is the DC input voltage

Φ is the phase angle between shunt capacitor voltage and load current.

The shunt capacitance, C_p , is given by

$$C_p = -\frac{2 \sin 2\phi}{\omega R \pi^2} \quad (2)$$

Where $\omega = 2\pi f$ and f is the switching frequency.

The inductance, L_{ext} , is described by

$$L_{ext} = \frac{R}{\omega} \left(\cot \phi - \frac{\pi^2}{4} \csc 2\phi \right) \quad (3)$$

The series resonant components, C_1 , are given by

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{\omega(QR - \omega L_{ext})} \quad (4)$$

$$L = \frac{QR}{\omega} \quad (5)$$

Where Q is the load quality factor.

III. CAPACITIVE POWER TRANSFER SYSTEM

a. Schematic of capacitive power transfer system

In this section, a capacitive power transfer system has been proposed as shown in Figure 2.

As seen in Figure 2 series capacitors, C_{11} and C_{12} , are defined as function of the coupling plates. A is the area of the plates and d is the distance between plates. The relation between d and A can be described by

$$C = \frac{\epsilon A}{d} \quad (6)$$

Where ϵ is the permittivity of the dielectric material in between the two conductive plates. The capacitance of both the forward and return capacitor will change when the distance varies. Thus, C_{11} and C_{12} can be combined into a single capacitor for convenience, that is,

$$C_1 = \frac{C_{11}C_{12}}{C_{11} + C_{12}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 2. CPT system using Class-E approach

a.i. Transmitter of CPT system

Transmitter of capacitive power system has been proposed, as shown in Figure 3, which can generate AC voltage from DC voltage. Therefore, AC voltage can flow through coupling capacitor.

Figure 3. Transmitter of Class-E amplifier

a.ii. Receiver of CPT system

Figure 4 shows the schematic of receiver in CPT system with Class-E amplifier approach. As seen in Figure 4, the rectifier, matching network and boost converter make up receiver of CPT system.

Figure 4. Schematic of receiver in CPT system with Class-E amplifier approach

The rectifier converts AC to DC voltage which can be increased to a high level by boost converter. Maximum power can be transferred by matching network between RF energy and its load [12]. Device protection is the second reason why matching network is used [15].

b. Output capacitance of MOSFET

This paper presents a CPT system with Class-E amplifier approach based on high switching frequency. Power dissipation through output capacitance has been deemed insignificant in the MOSFET. However, output capacitance need to be considered in the high switching frequency [16]. It begins to affect system efficiency as frequency increases. Thus, this capacitance becomes more important.

MOSFET parasitic parameters, such as inductance and capacitance, should be well defined in order to transfer power as operating frequency moves upward. Based on the design proposed in this paper, as shown in Figure 3, shunt capacitance is needed to be decreased mainly because output capacitance of MOSFET under high operating frequency can be used to compensate shunt capacitance.

c. Drive circuit of MOSFET design

A crystal unit which is designed to operate with a specified value of load capacitance can be used as a parallel resonant oscillator circuit. Figure 5 shows a parallel crystal circuit which uses a single inverter with two capacitors in the feedback loop. These two capacitors, defined as load

capacitance, establish the frequency that oscillator operates together with the crystal unit. The operating frequency will change when the value of load capacitance varies. The function of R_1 is to bias the inverter and to make the circuit work in its linear region. R_2 is used to bias the crystal unit. The function of two load capacitors, C_{L1} and C_{L2} , are used to sever to establish the frequency desired so that the oscillator will operate. X_1 is a crystal unit.

Figure 5. Parallel resonant oscillator circuit

Load capacitance, C_L , as described as a specified value of load capacitance, can be calculated in the case of a parallel resonant oscillator circuit. The calculation of the value of this capacitance as following equation

$$C_L = \frac{C_{L1} \times C_{L2}}{C_{L1} + C_{L2}} + C_s \quad (8)$$

Where,

C_{L1} and C_{L2} are the load capacitors

C_s is the circuit stray capacitance, usually 3 to 5 pF.

The sum of shunt capacitance of crystal, C_0 , and load capacitance C_L , is given by

$$C_t = C_0 + C_L \quad (9)$$

For the crystal unit, the series resonant frequency, f_s , is donated as

$$f_s = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_1 C_1}} \quad (10)$$

Where,

L_1 is motional inductance which represents the vibrating mass of the crystal unit.

C_1 is motional capacitance which represents the elasticity of the quartz.

Meanwhile, load resonant frequency, f_L , can be described as

$$f_L = \frac{1}{2\pi \sqrt{\frac{C_t C_1}{C_t + C_1} L_1}} \quad (11)$$

d. Design of load matching network

Assuming the components are ideal, L shape matching network can be achieved by using capacitors and inductors. Figure 6 shows basic L shape matching network.

Figure 6. Basic L shape matching network

As seen in figure 6, R_p can be matching by putting an inductor in series and paralleling with a capacitor, which generate to a load R_s .

Then, the inductance and capacitance can be calculated by following equation

$$X1 = \sqrt{(R_s R_p) - R_p^2} \quad (12)$$

$$X2 = R_s \frac{R_p}{X1} \quad (13)$$

Where $R_s > R_p$ is assumed.

e. Design of boost converter

Output of the rectifier, as shown in figure 2, provides a DC voltage to the boost converter. A good choice of the inductor, L_0 , as proposed in [14], is

$$L_0 > \frac{V_i(V_0 - V_i)}{\Delta I_L f_s V_0} \quad (14)$$

Where,

V_i is the typical input voltage.

f_s is the minimum switch frequency of the converter.

$$\Delta I_L = a I_{0(max)} \frac{V_0}{V_i} \quad (15)$$

Where,

$I_{0(max)}$ is the maximum output current necessary in the application.

The value of a can be chose between 0.2 to 0.4

The output capacitance, C_2 , is given by

$$C_2 > \frac{I_{0(max)} D_1}{f_s \Delta V_0} \quad (16)$$

Where

ΔV_0 is the desired output voltage ripple.

IV. SIMULATION

a. Calculation of complete capacitive power transfer system

A complete capacitive power transfer system with Class-E amplifier approach is implemented in LTSPICE. The schematic of the complete circuit is displayed in Figure 7. The following specifications were used in the design:

Figure 7. The schematic of the complete circuit

The series coupling capacitance, $C_{31} = C_{32} = 25\text{pF}$. From (7), $C_3 = \frac{C_{31}C_{32}}{C_{31}+C_{32}} = 12.5\text{pF}$. The operating frequency $f = 4\text{MHZ}$, DC power supply $V_{cc} = 15\text{V}$, desired output power $P_0 = 4.2\text{W}$. For the matching network, $R_s = 15000\Omega$ and $R_p = 22\Omega$. Load resistor, $R = 15000\Omega$.

From (12) and (13),

$$X1 = \sqrt{((R_s R_p) - R_p^2)} = \sqrt{((15000 \times 22) - 22^2)} = j574.88\Omega$$

$$X2 = R_s \frac{R_p}{X1} = 15000 \times \frac{22}{j574.88} = -574.03\Omega$$

Thus, for the matching network, the inductance of matching network $L_m = \frac{X_1}{2\pi f} = 22.84\mu\text{H}$ and

the capacitance of matching network $C_m = \frac{1}{2\pi f X_2} = 69.2\text{pF}$.

From (11), the equivalent load resistance $R_t = 39.44\Omega$.

By multiplying V_{cc} to both side of (1) and rearranging it,

$$\cos\phi = \frac{\pi}{V_{cc}} \sqrt{\frac{P_o R}{8}} = \frac{\pi}{15} \sqrt{\frac{4.2 \times 39.44}{8}} = 0.9531 \quad (17)$$

Hence, $\phi = -17.63^\circ$.

From (2), the shunt capacitor

$$C_1 = -\frac{2\sin 2\phi}{\omega\pi^2 R_t} = 118\text{pF}$$

Form (3),

$$\omega L_{ext} = R_t \left(\cot\phi - \frac{\pi^2}{4} \csc 2\phi \right) = 44.47 \quad (18)$$

By using (4) gives,

$$Q = \frac{1 + \omega^2 C_1 L_{ext}}{\omega C_1 R_t} = 21 \quad (19)$$

Employing (5) renders,

$$L = \frac{R_t Q}{\omega} = 33.02\mu\text{H}$$

The parameters of the circuit in this case were based on the additional capacitor. Quality factor Q should be no more than 20 in order to get better performance.

b. Simulation of transmitter of CPT system

Simulation circuit of transmitter of CPT system can be seen in Figure 8. C_1 is shunt capacitor, C_{31} and C_{32} are coupling capacitors.

Figure 8. Transmitter of CPT system

Figure 9 and 10 show the typical waveform of the DC supply current. The proposed transmitter of CPT system is able to operate the system under the ZVS condition regardless of the non-constant DC current.

Figure 9. Waveforms of DC supply current

Figure 10. Waveforms of drain voltage and switch voltage

Figure 11 shows the waveform of AC voltage which generate from DC supply voltage by Class-E amplifier of CPT system. Therefore, this voltage can flow through coupling capacitor C_{31} and C_{32} .

Figure 11. AC voltage across load R_s

c. Simulation of Class-E amplifier with load matching network

Figure 12 shows the circuit of the Class-E amplifier with load matching network. R_s , illustrated in Figure 8, can be replaced by an L matching network. Equivalent circuit is given in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Circuit of Class-E amplifier with load matching network

Simulation result can be seen in Figure 13; by using the matching network, ZVS condition can also be achieved.

Figure 13. Waveforms of drain voltage and switch voltage with matching network

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A prototype of the Class-E amplifier with additional capacitor based capacitive power transfer system is implemented as shown in Figure 14 in order to check the validity of the simulated design.

Figure 14. Implementation of CPT system

As seen in Figure 14, two parallel sets of copper plates form the forward and the returning capacitor which are C_{31} and C_{32} . The capacitance of these two coupling capacitors are given by

$$C = \varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 \frac{A}{d} \quad (20)$$

Where

ε_r is the relativity dielectric constant of the material between the plates.

ε_0 is the permittivity of free space ($\varepsilon_0 \approx 8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ Fm}^{-1}$).

A is the overlapping area of the two plates and d is the gap between the plates.

In this experiment, the shape of the plate for the forward capacitor is a circle and for the returning capacitor it is annular shaped. The dimensions of the copper plates are chosen to be 11.94cm^2 and 28.27cm^2 and the thickness of the plastic films is 1mm. The forward capacitance is 9.5pF and the returning capacitance is 19.8pF . Thus, from (7), the series capacitance of C_{31} and C_{32} is determined to be

$$C_3 = \frac{C_{31}C_{32}}{C_{31} + C_{32}} = 6.4\text{pF}$$

The measured value of C_3 is roughly 6.25pF .

By using the same specifications of design in the simulation with two pieces of plastic films in between the plates, the waveforms of the shunt capacitor voltage can be seen in Figure 15. As

shown in this figure, the ZVS condition is achieved. Table 1 shows the theoretical calculated component values compared to the experimental measured values.

Figure 15. Waveforms of shunt capacitor and switch voltage

Table 1. Comparison between theoretical calculated values and experimental values for CPT system

	C_1	C_3	L	Efficiency	C_1
Theoretical calculated	$6.4pF$	$190pF$	$32.5\mu H$	100%	$4.2W$
Experimental measured	$6.25pF$	$125pF$	$33.02\mu H$	83%	$4W$

The operating frequency in this experiment is $4MHz$. The lower power transfer efficiency is due to the ferrite core being used as the tuning inductor. This may result in losses in high frequency and losses in gate driver. The difference in the value with the calculation of shunt capacitor is mainly due to the nonlinear characteristic of MOSFET's drain source capacitance.

Based on capacitive power transfer system proposed above, a wireless LED lamp shown in Figure 16 has been constructed to demonstrate a working scaled prototype of the simulated system which validated the fundamental concepts. The lamp consists of a transmitter, a receiver and a 15V DC power supply.

Figure16. Wireless LED lamp with CPT system

For the design of the transmitter of the LED lamp, the Class-E inverter and the forward capacitors are all set in the square box which is supplied by the 15V DC voltage. Figure 17 shows inside of transmitter.

Figure 17. Circuit of transmitter for LED lamp

For the design of the receiver of the LED lamp, the returning capacitors, the load matching network, the rectifier and the boost converter are all set in the secondary prototype with the LED lamp. Figure 18 shows inside of the receiver.

Figure 18. Circuit of receiver for LED lamp

Power has been successfully transferred from the transmitter to the receiver wirelessly by the use of CPT as shown in Figure 19. The LED lamp has been lit successfully showing wireless power transfer through CPT.

Figure 19. Demonstration of wireless LED lamp with CPT system

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the design of a capacitive power transfer system based on a Class-E inverter approach has been presented. This implies that the proposed capacitive power transfer system is

able to transfer power with high efficiency. In the demonstration, the LED lamp is successfully lit to show a working wireless power transfer system used in the application of LED lighting via CPT. Finally, the design procedure proposed above has been verified both in simulations and experimental settings.

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